

LOW DIELECTRIC CONSTANT NANOCOMPOSITE FIBER MATS PRODUCED BY ELECTROSPINNING

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ABSTRACT: Multifunctional nanofibers can be produced by an electrostatic spinning process where a high voltage is applied between a polymer solution containing functional nanoparticles and a ground plate at a distance. Currently, the process is being optimized by varying process parameters, such as polymer solution concentration, electro voltage, collector distance, and nanoparticle volume fraction.

In microelectronic applications, low dielectric constant material is actively sought for reducing the resistance-capacitance (RC) time delay of inter-connects and cross talk between metal lines. One of promising methods is to introduce porosity into low dielectric constant materials.

Ultra-low dielectric constant fibrous film is fabricated from such electrospinning process with Polyacrylonitrile (PAN). High porous film with an average of 83% porosity can be readily obtained. The measured dielectric constants show values between 1.4~1.6 compared to the current low dielectric constant material of 2.2. By electrospinning with nanoparticles the dielectric constant is further reduced. The added functional nanoparticles may also have various functional enhancements, such as strength and toughness to meet the application requirements. Several nanoparticles such as iron oxide, graphite nanoplatelet, and carbon nanotube are investigating for its applicable functionality.

KEYWORDS: electrospinning, multi-functional nanocomposite, nanoparticles

1. INTRODUCTION

A medium with a low dielectric constant will result in a higher signal propagation speed since signal speed is inversely proportional to the square root of the dielectric constant. Materials with high dielectric constants are suitable for capacitor applications whereas low dielectric constant materials are used in microelectronics and integrated circuit applications¹. Major advances in fast and powerful micro-electronic devices have been made possible through device miniaturization. As the devices become smaller, the inter-metal dielectric (IMD) must be lower in order to reduce the resistance-capacitance (RC) time delay of interconnects and cross talk between metal lines. It is well known that the benefits derived from the use of low dielectric materials are far greater than those from increasing the conductivity of the metal interconnects.

Accordingly, there is an active search for low dielectric constant materials. The materials that have been proposed include fluorinated silica glass², air gap formation³, porous silica materials through Aerogel or Xerogel^{4,5}, porous polymers such as methyl silsesquioxane⁶, Parylene-F-like film⁷, and poly(arylethers)⁸. In addition to the low dielectric constant requirement, major challenges include obtaining low dielectric constant materials that have adequate mechanical strength as well as chemical and thermal properties, and are amenable to manufacturing integration⁹. Currently, the processes being used to produce low dielectric constant materials are Spin-on dielectric (SOD) and Chemical vapor deposition (CVD), including plasma enhanced CVD. A summary of the structure and properties of these low dielectric constant materials are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of current and future low K material

Process	Materials	Dielectric Constant	Remark/vendor
CVD	SiO ₂	4.2-4.5	
		Low-K	
CVD	FSG	3.6-3.9	
SOD	HSQ	2.9-3.6	DOW
SOD	MSQ	2.9-3.1	DOW
SOD	Spin-on glass	2.7-3.1	
SOD	Fluorinated polyimide	2.6-2.9	
SOD	Poly(arylene ethers)	2.6-2.9	Allied Signal
SOD	PTFE	1.9-2.1	Gore
SOD	SiLK	~2.6	DOW
CVD	Parylene N	2.6-2.8	Novellas
CVD	OSG	2.8-3.0	Applied Materials
CVD	Black Diamond	~2.7	Applied Materials
		Porous Material	
SOD	Nanoglass	1.3~2.5	Allied Signal
SOD	Porous SiLK	~2.1	DOW
SOD	Polyimide nanofoams	~2.2	
SOD	Silica aerogels/Xerogel	1.5-2.2	
SOD	PolyELK	<2.2	Schumacher
SOD	Nanoporus Silica	1.3-2.5	

An examination of the state-of-the-art low dielectric constant materials reveals that their common feature is high porosity as the lowest dielectric constant is realized in vacuum. Furthermore, they tend to be rigid and brittle, and lack adequate strength to endure the handling during subsequent processing.

The present paper reports a new class of ultra-low dielectric constant materials based on nanocomposite fibers produced by the electrospinning process. Having a submicron diameter, the electrospun fiber mats yield a high level of porosity while covering a wide area. The fibrous nature of the mat lends itself to a flexible and conformable structure. Furthermore, the mechanical, chemical and thermal properties of the fiber mats can be tailored by introducing another phase such as nanoparticles, nanoplatelets and nanotubes. The processing, structure and properties of these nanocomposite fiber mats are described in the present paper.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Electrospinning Process

The electrostatic spinning or electrospinning process is a simple and non-mechanical process analogous to electro-spraying developed some sixty years ago¹⁰. Because of its simplicity and its capability to generate nanoscale fibers from polymer solutions and melts under ambient conditions there is a revival of interest in

the electrospinning process to create structures that have ultra-high surface areas^{11,12}. In the electrospinning process as illustrated in Figure 1, an electric field is generated between a polymer solution and a metal collection screen. The polymer solution is contained in a syringe with a steel capillary tip and a voltage is applied between the tip and the conductive collector. As the electrical potential is increased, the charged polymer solution is attracted to the collector. When the voltage reaches a critical value, the charge overcomes the surface tension of the polymer formed on the capillary tip and a jet with a diameter ranging from 50~500 nm have been produced¹¹. As the charged jet flies through the air, it loses the solvent through quick evaporation and impinges on the collection screen as a thin fiber mat. The fiber diameter can be controlled by varying the charge density and the polymer solution concentration. Addition of nanoparticles to the polymer solution yields the desired nanocomposite mat.

Figure 0: Schematic representation of Electrospinning process

2.2 Nanocomposite Fiber Mat Fabrication

To electrospin a neat resin fiber mat, a polymer solution was prepared by dissolving 7% by weight of Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) powder in N,N,-Dimethyl Formamide (DMF) under sonication for 20 minutes. The final solution was clear and viscous. As for nanocomposite fiber mats, nanoparticles amounting to 1-4% by weight of PAN was first added to DMF solvent, followed by the PAN powder. To avoid the possibility of polymer degradation, the temperature rise during sonication was kept below 60°C by using a water bath. Two types of nanoparticles were used: iron oxide (magnemite from Nanophase), graphite nanoplateles (courtesy of Dr. Richard Kaner, UCLA). The nominal sizes of these nanoparticles are summarized in Table 2.

The voltage applied was 20 kV and the distance from the syringe tip to the collector plate was 15 cm. The collector plate was covered with an aluminum foil 7.5 x 7.5 cm square. Each fiber mat was collected on the aluminum foil for about 3 hours in order to have sufficient thickness for the subsequent characterization. The thickness thus obtained was 0.3 mm in average. In addition, solid discs of neat PAN and nanocomposites solid discs were cast and dried from the same solutions for comparison purposes.

2.3 Dielectric Constant Measurement

Dielectric constants of the electrospun fiber mats were measured on an Agilent 4263B LCR Meter with a 16451B Dielectric Test Fixture. Electrode B was used with a required sample diameter between 10 mm and 50 mm. In order to facilitate comparison of test results, circular specimens were prepared with a nominal diameter of 12.5 mm. Specimen thickness was determined by taking an average of three measurements using a digital micrometer. As the specimens were flexible, two cover glasses were used to sandwich each sample with a predetermined pressure from the digital micrometer. All measurements were made by setting the LCR meter with test signal level of 1V over the available frequency range of 1, 10 and 100 kHz. Non-contact or air-gap method was used for all measurements. By measuring the capacitance with and without a

specimen, the concern for the possible effect of air gap between the electrode and test sample specimen is eliminated. The dielectric constants were calculated using the equation given by the manufacture¹³.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of Nanoparticles on Processing

The addition of nanoparticles has a large influence on the solution viscosity. When the nanoparticle loading is increased, the viscosity also increases. Figure 2 shows some of the measured solution viscosity. Increased viscosity will have a profound effect on the electrospinning process. When viscosity is too high, the solution does not flow easily and dries up in the tip due to the faster solvent evaporation stopping the process.

In case of iron oxide particles, up to 4% loading does not affect the process much. The flexibility of the fiber mat is dramatically decreased when the particle loading is more than 4%. At 8% loading the fiber mat becomes separated and the fibers are not as continuous as in the lower loading cases. A high particle loading appears to hinder the formation of long fiber.

When graphite nanoplatelets (GNP) are used, the resulting viscosity increase is less than that observed when iron oxide particles are used as in Figure 2. Consequently, the maximum particle loading is higher.

Figure 1: Viscosity change due to addition

of nanoparticles.
Table 3: Calculated Porosity of nanofiber mats

Material	Solid Density	Fiber Mat Density	Porosity
PAN ²	1087.19	307.36	71.73%
PAN/ Fe ₂ O ₃ -2%	1111.63	370.27	84.68%
PAN/ GNP-2%	1058.82	182.48	82.77%

3.2 Porosity Estimation

The specific densities of the electrospun fiber mat and the solid disc can be calculated by dividing the sample weight with its measured volume. The porosity of the electrospun fiber mat can then be derived from the ratio of the specific density of spun fiber mat to that of the cast sample. Table 3 lists some calculated results. The porosities of the fiber mats appear to be between 70~90% and has an average porosity of 0.823.

The pores in electrospun fiber mats are generated by the intertwined fibers. The brittleness inherent in porous bulk materials is not observed in electrospun fiber mats. Even with high porosity, the fiber mats still provide the flexibility required for handling.

3.3 SEM Examinations

Figures 3 and 4 show the SEM micrographs of neat PAN and PAN/iron-oxide fiber mats. No fiber ends can be seen in the micrographs. The continuity of fibers in the fiber mats contributes to the flexibility of the mat even with a very high porosity. From the pictures, the PAN fiber mat has fiber diameters of 200nm on average. The addition of iron oxide nanoparticles reduces the fiber diameter to about 150nm. The neat PAN fiber mat has a higher density than that of PAN/iron oxide fiber mats and well matches to the porosity measurements in Table 3.

Figure 3 SEM of PAN/Fe₂O₃-2% nanofibers

3.4 Reduction of Dielectric Constant

Dielectric constants of PAN/iron oxide were measured at 1, 10, and 100 k HZ in Figure 5. By comparison, the spun PAN has about 39% lower value than the cast PAN. PAN based nanocomposite fiber mat has a further reduction of 12% to the pure spun PAN nanofiber mat. The dielectric constants appear to decrease with increasing particle loading regardless of the test frequency. In all cases, electrospun fiber mats exhibit lower dielectric constants than the state-of-the-art low dielectric materials (1.4 ~ 2.1)¹⁴.

Figure 24 Dielectric Constant comparison of different materials

It is known that by introducing porosity into material, dielectric constant can be greatly reduced. In the extreme cases, the upper and lower bound values for the corresponding situation can be modeled as parallel and serial connection of composite materials involved as following¹⁵:

Upper bound: Parallel connection

$$\varepsilon_{tp} = x \cdot \varepsilon_1 + (1 - x) \cdot \varepsilon_2 = x + (1 - x) \cdot \varepsilon_2$$

Lower bound: Serial connection

$$\frac{1}{\varepsilon_{ts}} = \frac{x}{\varepsilon_1} + \frac{(1-x)}{\varepsilon_2} = \frac{x \cdot \varepsilon_2 + (1-x) \cdot \varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_1 \cdot \varepsilon_2},$$

where ε = Dielectric constant, and x is the porosity. Since the pores are mostly filled with air that has a dielectric constant of nearly one, ε_1 can be normally omitted.

For the electrospun mat, the structure of the material is composed of individually oriented fibers instead of bulk material. If the orientation of fibers in the layer is perpendicular to the measuring direction, the effect on dielectric constant will be more closely attributed to the parallel connection. The built up layers, on the other hand, will be parallel to the measuring direction and thus attributed to serial connection.

Therefore, fiber layer effective flatness y can be defined as the percentage of fibers lying parallel to measuring electrodes. Then, $y=1$ when fibers are all flat, and $y=0$ when fiber are vertical. By assuming the linear effect on the combination effect of parallel and serial connection due to fiber orientation, the resulted dielectric constant would be written as

$$\varepsilon_f = y * \varepsilon_{ts} + (1 - y) * \varepsilon_{tp} ,$$

where ε_f is the effective dielectric constant of nanocomposite.

The SEM examinations of Figures 3 and 4 depict that most of fibers are lying flat and only a small portion of the fibers will be in a stacking condition. Therefore, a large y can be expected. The value of y is difficult to measure as the fiber is tangled. A fitting of $y=0.8$ gives a very good fitting of measured data as in Figure 6.

Figure 3: Comparison of various dielectric Constant models. Parallel and serial data are based on PAN (K=4.0)

From the above analysis it can be seen that the dielectric constant of electrospun fiber mats tend to approach the limit of series connection of polymer matrix and air with high porosity. This phenomenon indicates that the dielectric constant of polymer matrix materials may have a limited effect on the final dielectric constant of fiber mats. Doubling the value of dielectric constant of the polymer material can have only a 14% increase on the spun fiber mats. And since the dielectric constant is already in the ultra low region, this increase is even more negligible. This implies that high dielectric constant, high performance polymer materials may also be utilized while retaining similar low dielectric constant property. The allowable selection of other higher dielectric constant material can be judicious for the manufacturing process as various improvements and enhancements can be readily available through other materials that may have a higher dielectric constant. The flexibility on the chosen materials may mitigate the possible integration issues in the subsequent microelectronic manufacturing process. Poly(arylethers), one of the high performance thermoset polymer material, is currently under evaluation.

Further reduction of dielectric constant from the addition of nanoparticles can be seen in Table 4. Although iron oxide powders have higher dielectric constant (~14) compared to PAN (~4), the decrease in dielectric constant from the increased porosity outweighs the increase from this material property difference.

3.5 Other Nanoparticles

Different nanoparticles are also tested, including graphite platelet, zinc oxide and tin oxide. They all have similar effects on the effective dielectric constant as from iron oxide. For graphite nanoplatelet (GNP) the increase on the solution viscosity is much less and particle loading can be substantially higher. This difference may be due to the different topology of graphite nanoplatelet and iron oxide nanoparticles. Also, since graphite nanoplatelets have relatively high conductivity when compared with other nanoparticles, the electrospun PAN/Graphite nanoplatelet fiber mat exhibits an even lower dielectric constant as in Table 4.

Addition of nanoparticles also provides another avenue of functional enhancements. For instance, mechanical strength can also be enhanced through the addition of graphite nanoplatelets and carbon nanotubes. These functional effects from various nanoparticles can further increase the applicability of electrospun fibers.

4. CONCLUSION

Ultra low Dielectric Constant porous nanocomposite fiber mats were fabricated from electrospinning process. The fiber mats have a huge porous network formed by multilayer spun nanofiber. The continuous fiber and layer structure give the fiber mat very flexible in spite of this large porosity. Fabricated nanocomposite fiber mats are characterized and the reduction of K with porosity formed by fibers are modeled and fit to the experimental data. The result reveals that the K of the polymer matrix is only a minor effect in this case and higher performance polymer may be used even with a relatively high K value.

Inclusion of nanoparticles can have many different effects. Particle loading will increase the viscosity of solution and influence electrospinning process and subsequently, the formation of fiber mat. Mixing of iron oxide nanoparticles found to decrease the fiber diameters and increase the porosity compared to pure nanofiber mat. But higher loading of nanoparticles may hinder the formation of fiber mats.

Nanoparticles also serve as an enhancement of various functionalities, such as mechanical strength and magnetic properties. Different nanoparticles are currently studied for various functional effects.

As lower dielectric constant materials are continuously sought to advance microelectronics, the electrospun nanocomposite fiber mats provide one of the promising choices of candidate materials.

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